

PROFITABILITY AND CONSTRAINTS OF GARDEN-EGG PRODUCTION IN ISIALA-
NGWA AREA OF ABIA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the profitability and constraints encountered by garden-egg farmers in Isiala-Ngwa areas of Abia State. A multi-stage purposive sampling technique was adopted to select the 118 respondents used in the study out of a total of 1180 farmers. Descriptive statistic and gross margin analysis were employed to analyze the data from the study area. The study revealed that the 3 categories of farmers, that is, those cultivating less than 1 hectare had a gross margin of ₦70, 370.30 while those cultivating between 1 to 4 hectare had a gross margin of ₦197, 866.00 and for all those cultivating garden-egg in the area had a gross margin of ₦338, 606.08, with productivity index of 1.93, 1.67 and 1.75 respectively, indicating a positive return on investment. Also revealed are the various perceived constraints of the farmers which include, storage facilities, marketing problem, pest and diseases etc. from the viewpoint of this study, garden-egg production is a profitable enterprise in the study area.

KEYWORDS: Constraints, Garden-egg, Profitability, Productivity index,

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INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is the mainstay of the small scale farmers in Nigeria. Giron et al (2010) had posited that Agricultural production is dominated by small scale farmers and is known to produce more than 90% of food consumed in the country. One of the items of production is garden-egg (*Solanum melongena*) cultivated mostly by subsistence farmers under rain fed low input practices and in mixture with other crops. There are however evidence of its commercial production in the study area. Garden-egg is known to supplement starchy foods in addition to being a cheap source of protein, minerals and vitamins. The leaves of some species are also used as vegetables and the alkaloid called “solanin” is extracted from the roots, leaves and fruits of garden-egg for therapeutic purposes (PROTA, 2004).

In Southeastern Nigeria, the leaves and fruits are used in the preparation of different local or indigenous delicacies such as the local Igbo salad made of oil bean slices (Ugba in Igbo) and tapioca or abacha (processed cassava slices). The fruits can also be eaten raw accompanied by groundnut paste.

However the yield of garden-egg varies depending on the climate, the variety and the growing techniques. According to PROTA (2004), one plant may produce from 500g to about 8kg of fruits, depending on the cultivars and growing conditions. Improved cultivars grown under favorable conditions may yield between 50-80 tonnes per hectare. Garden-egg production can be a profitable venture but it also involves risks, which farmers regards as problem militating against its massive production. Most farmers do not regard garden-egg production as profitable due to the risk involved therefore cannot readily sacrifice their scarce resources in its production on a large scale. There is need to convince the farmer of its profitable nature in order for him to abandon his age-long practice. In this study, the researcher seeks to determine the profitability and challenges’ facing the average garden-egg farmer since garden-egg production has a great impact on the nutritional, socio-cultural, socio-economic and the environmental lives of millions of people.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Isiala-Ngwa North and South of Abia State in 2009. Isiala-Ngwa North occupies a land mass of 283km² with a population of 153,734 while Isiala-Ngwa South occupies a land mass of 258km² with a total population of 134,762 (Wikipedia, 2007). Abia State lies between latitude 04^o45¹ and 06^o17¹ North and Longitude 07^o00¹ and 08^o00¹ East (Abia ADP, 2005).

Multi-stage purposive sampling technique was used to select a sample of 118 garden-egg producer households from a pre-survey sampling frame of 1180 farmers from 18 garden-egg producing communities in the local government areas. This was done through the list of registered garden-egg farmers with the Abia Agricultural development programme (ADP). The sampling distribution of the respondents is shown in Table 1. One hundred and eighteen (118) farmers were administered with the questionnaires.

Descriptive and inferential statistic and gross margin analysis were the analytical tools employed to achieve the research objectives.

$$\text{Gross Margin (GM)} = \text{Total revenue (TR)} - \text{Total cost (TC)}$$

Table 1: Sampling distribution of respondents in the study areas

Names of communities where garden-egg is produced	Number of garden-egg producers from their different communities registered with ADP	10% of the population of garden-egg farmers	Number of respondents administered
Umuofima	60	6	6
Umuekea	70	7	7
Nvosi	80	8	8
Owerri Ata	60	6	6
Ntigha	70	7	7
Ihie	60	6	6
Urata	60	6	5
Nkputa	50	5	6
Umuala	60	6	6
Noli	60	6	6
Umuichima	80	8	8
Amaekpu	70	7	7
Mgbede ala	60	6	6
Mgbede oda	60	6	6
Ichi	50	5	5
Amaoji	80	8	8
Okpuala	80	8	8
Akpara	70	7	7
Total	1180	118	118

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2, shows the age distribution of the respondents in the study area. The productivity and output of the farmer is expected to be affected by his age, Adewumi and Omotesho (2002). Age of the farmer also affects the adoption of innovation in traditional farming system. The mean age of the respondents is 44.5 years which is within the age range of 40-49 years. This might have implication for available family labor. The aging nature of the respondents shows that there might be a reduction in the effective labor force for agricultural production in the study area in the near future. It was also observed that eighty-six (86) out of the one hundred and eighteen respondents (118) are male, only thirty-two (32) are female. Male dominance in the business of garden-egg in the study area is a reflection of the importance of the crop. Garden-egg production is a money spinner in the study area, thus majority are full time farmers 59.32% while 40.68% are part-time farmers. This is an indication

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that garden-egg production is an importance component in the plural enterprise system. The study also revealed that all respondents (100%) had one form of education or the other but 59.32% had secondary education which is an indication that all the respondents are in a position to understand and adopt available innovation that encourage increases in garden-egg production. The productive efficiency of the farmer to a great extent is affected by his years of experience. The farmers years of experience ranges between 3 to 18 years, this is a reasonable period which would have exposed them to a lot of challenges in the production process and therefore would have found adaptive strategies to those challenges hence better productivity. More than 90% of farmers in the study area grew their garden-egg on the flat after raising it in the nursery. Ngwa lands are well drained and could support crops growth without much tillage; few other farmers went the extra mile of providing ridges (25.5%) and beds (0.9%). The analysis further revealed that most farmers are small land holders, only 0.85% had farms that are 4 hectares and above. Majority of the farmers 71.9% had farms less than one hectare.

The mean farm size of 0.5 hectares agrees with the previous findings that majority of farmers in sub-Saharan Africa are small holders of farm size of less than 6 hectares (Olayide, 1980; Ogunbile and Olukosi, (1991), Nwaiwu, 2007). The farm size is an indication that production is at a subsistence level. Majority of the garden-egg farmers (68%) had access to extension services while 32% did not. Access to agricultural extension services is dynamic, it is expected that more farmers would also come in contact with extension services over time.

The study also shows that 30% of the respondents depended on borrowed money for production while 70% used their personal savings to finance the production of the crop. This indicates that garden-egg production in the previous years had left a surplus to the majority of the farmers that enabled them to save enough money to finance the production activities in the following year.

CONSTRAINTS TO GARDEN-EGG PRODUCTION

The constraints confronting garden-egg production as perceived by farmers are presented in Table 3. The result shows that 34 of the respondents in the study area complained of lack of storage facilities especially at the peak of their harvesting, because of this problem they were forced to sell at low prices, sometimes not making profit. 20% of the respondents had the problem of irrigation facilities. The farmers lamented that garden-egg production in the dry season would attract more profit and would be done at least cost. Another identified constraint is weed control, 19 respondents representing 16% spent so much on weeding, which has the potential of increasing the production cost and thereby reducing the revenue accruing to the farmer, this is an indication of high cost of labor. According to Olayide and Heady (1982), labor is the second most important resource in farm production and constitutes a serious limiting input in the production process. Fourteen percent (14%) of the respondents could not borrow money due to reasons which ranged from lack of collateral security required by lenders to lack of guarantors.

Control of pests and disease was another source of problem to the farmer in the study area. Nine (9) respondents representing 8% in the study area complained bitterly of losing so much to insects/pests attack. Vegetable crops are subjected to a variety of pests and disease that can reduce yield and quality of the crop (Ibrahim, 2005).

The high cost of transportation in the study area acts as a constraint to effective marketing of the produce, sixteen (16) respondents constituting 13.56% of the farmers stated that marketing of garden-egg was expensive because of transportation costs. Sometimes the farmers in the area will transport themselves to the market at a high cost where they sometimes sell at a loss. Hence many of these farmers sold their produce at the farm gate thereby resulting in low revenue.

It appears production of Garden-egg in the study area is profitable, thus opportunities still exist for improvement if the constraints as highlighted by the respondents are adequately addressed and strategies designed to alleviate them.

GROSS MARGIN ANALYSIS

In any production process, costs are incurred in production output while returns are earned from the sales of such output. Table 4, presents the average variable cost incurred by all the farmers in the study area, that is,

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those that cultivated less than 1 hectare, from 1 to 4 hectares and that by all the farmers of garden-egg in the area. From the Table it can be seen that those that cultivated less than a hectare incurred a cost of ₦152,095.00 while for those who cultivated between 1 to 4 hectare was ₦296,586.0 and for all the garden-egg farmers it was ₦448,681.00.

The revenue from the sales of the produce was calculated based on the prevailing market price to be ₦292, 835.60 for those farmers who cultivated less than 1 hectare while those who cultivated between 1 to 4 hectare had a revenue of ₦494, 452.00 and for all they garden-egg farmers in the area had a total revenue value of ₦787, 287.60.

Gross margin is simply subtracting the cost of production from the revenue generated, meant to reveal the cost incurred and the revenue generated by the producer to determine whether it is a viable venture or not. It is usually done to determine the possible contribution of the enterprise to the total farm income in the farming system of the area. Thus, the gross margin for farmers who cultivated less than a hectare of garden-egg was ₦70, 370.30, those farmers that cultivated between 1 to 4 hectares of garden-egg had a gross margin of ₦197, 866.00 and all the farmers in the study area that cultivated garden-egg had a gross margin of ₦338, 606.08. The result of the gross margin shows a positive return on investment, these gave a productivity index of 1.93, 1.67 and 1.75 for the three groups of farmers respectively. This implies that for every one hundred naira invested by a farmer/producer in the production of Garden-egg in the study area, an additional income of ninety-three; sixty-seven and seventy-five naira were realized respectively indicating that Garden-egg production is a profitable venture in the study area.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of the data gathered in the course of the study revealed that most respondents were small holders of farm land and the production of garden-egg engage people of different productive age even though dominated by the male gender. Various constraints as perceived by the farmers were identified. They include, lack of storage facilities, pest and diseases, weed control, non-availability of irrigation facilities, marketing problem and in-adequate credit, and if addressed will go a long way in enhancing production, while the gross margin analysis shows a positive return on investment.

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Table 2: Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents in the Study Area

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage
AGE OF RESPONDENT		
20-29	20	16.95
30-39	29	24.58
40-49	42	35.59
50-59	17	14.41
60 and above	10	8.48
Total	118	100.00
GENDER		
Male	86	72.88
Female	32	27.12
Total	118	100.00
STATUS		
Full-time	70	59.32
Part-time	40	40.68
Total	118	100.00
EDUCATIONAL LEVEL		
Primary	33	27.97
Secondary	70	59.32
Tertiary	15	12.21
Total	118	100.00
Method of Land Preparation		
Flat	114	96.6
Ridges	3	2.54
Beds	1	0.9
Total	118	100.00
FARM SIZE (HA)		
0-1	84	71.9
1-2	22	18.64
2-3	6	5.08
3-4	4	3.39
4-5	1	0.85
Over 5 ha	1	0.85
Total	118	100.00
FARMING EXPERIENCE		
1-5	67	56.78
6-10	27	22.88
11-15	12	10.17
16-20	12	10.17
Total	118	100.00
EXTENSION SERVICE		
Yes	80	67.80
No	38	32.20
Total	118	100.00
CREDIT FACILITIES		
Borrowed Money	36	30.50
Did not Borrowed	82	69.50
Total	118	100.00

Table 3: Perceived Constraints of Respondents in the Study Area

Identified Constraints	Frequency	Percentage
No Storage Facilities	34	28.81
No Irrigation Facilities	24	20.34
Weed Control	19	16.10
Pest and Diseases	9	7.63
Marketing Problem	16	13.56
Inadequate Credit	16	13.56
Total	118	100.00

Table 4: Average Variable Cost Incurred By Farmers in the Study Area

ITEMS	AVERAGE VARIABLE COST (₦)		
	0-1ha	1-4ha	All Farmers
Renting of Land	10,400	20,280	30,680
Land of Preparation	18,600	36,270	54,870
Purchase of Fertilizer	36,260	70,207	106,167
Pest/disease control	24,090	46,976	71,066
Purchase of Seeds	12,600	24,570	24,570
Purchase of Seedlings	23,665	46,147	37,170
Field Operations (Planting, Maintenance and Harvesting)	12,100	23,595	35,695
Transportation	14,380	28,041	42,421
Total	152,095	296,586	448,681

